

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B411
 Date: 30 Oct 2008
 Take Off: 10:25:05
 Landing: 15:48:02
 Flight Time 5h22m57s

Campaign: VOCALS

Operating Area: South east pacific ocean off west coast of northern Chile

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Tracy Hill	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Steve Abel	Met Office	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
6	Mission Scientist 3	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
7	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
8	Core Chem / FTP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
10	SWS/SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
11	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
12	ARIES / MARSS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
13	AMS / SP2	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
14	Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
15	VACC	Mark Bart	Leeds University	
16	Manchester cloud	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
17	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
18	Mission Scientist 4	Alan Gadian	Leeds University	

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B411
 Date: 30/10/2008
 Project: VOCALS
 Location: Arica, Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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101826		!	0.09 kft	022	taxy
101925		!	0.09 kft	019	ASPs opened
102505		Take-off			
102505	103237	Profile 1	0.40 - 6.0 kft	200	
102921		!	3.0 kft	266	Nevzorov/JW zero
103058		!	4.7 kft	250	Heimann cal
103237	103739	Run 1	6.0 kft	261	
103733		!	6.0 kft	253	Nevzorov/JW zero
103744	104241	Profile 2	6.0 - 1.0 kft	252	
104242	104453	Profile 3	0.99 - 2.7 kft	249	
104453	105500	Run 2	2.7 kft	250	
105512	105609	Profile 4	2.6 - 1.8 kft	246	
105614	110611	Run 3	1.8 - 1.6 kft	247	
110619	110926	Profile 5	1.6 - 0.00 kft	251	
110933	111925	Run 4	0.1 kft	256	100 ft run
111457		!	0.1 kft	251	Heimann cal
111941	112920	Profile 6	0.05 - 8.9 kft	252	
112920	113709	Profile 7	8.9 - 0.89 kft	252	
113716	114044	Run 5	0.88 - 0.96 kft	244	
113809		!	0.88 kft	243	Nevzorov/JW zero
114052	114325	Profile 8	1.2 - 3.3 kft	030	
114326	115321	Run 6	3.5 kft	146	
115559	121536	Run 7	3.7 kft	336	
121558	121924	Profile 9	3.3 - 1.8 kft	353	
121938	124202	Run 8	1.9 - 1.8 kft	155	
122126		!	1.8 kft	156	Nevzorov/JW zero
124211	124518	Profile 10	1.6 - -.04 kft	151	
124524	130511	Run 9	-.04 - -.06 kft	333	QNH 1019
124721		!	-.06 kft	337	Heimann cal, Nevzorov/JW zero
130512	131021	Profile 11	-.06 - 4.9 kft	331	QNH 1019
131936		!	4.9 kft	154	Nevzorov/JW zero
132016		!	4.8 kft	205	Heimann cal
132436	132612	Run 10	4.9 - 4.8 kft	153	
132617	133240	Profile 12	4.8 - 0.05 kft	152	
133250	133716	Profile 13	0.05 - 4.3 kft	156	
133344		!	0.77 kft	152	Nevzorov zero

133734	134315	Profile 14	4.0 - 0.05 kft	154 50 ft
134138		!	0.45 kft	149 Nev JW zero
134324	134726	Profile 15	0.05 - 3.4 kft	156
134836	140212	Run 11	3.4 - 3.3 kft	339
140241	140406	Profile 16	3.4 - 3.7 kft	013
140531	142020	Run 12	3.7 kft	155
142031	142117	Profile 17	3.6 - 3.3 kft	157
142256	143250	Run 13	3.4 - 3.3 kft	329
143349	144444	Run 14	3.4 kft	084
144455	145313	Profile 18	3.5 - 10.0 kft	073

Fltsumm logging failed in flight, the following has been reconstructed post-flight.

145325	150458	Profile 19	10.0 - 0.05 kft	
150458	150510	Profile 20	0.05 - 0.1 kft	
150510	151510	Run 15	0.1 kft	
151510	151710	Profile 21	0.1 - 2.0 kft	
151710	152800	Run 16	2.0 kft	
152800	153130	Profile 22	2.0 - 4.5 kft	
153130	154220	Run 17	4.5 - 5.0 kft	
154220	154802	Profile 23	5.0 - 0.0 kft	
154802		Land		

B411 Track 30-OCT-08

FAAM Sortie, Flight B411
Thu 30th October 2008
VOCALS Flight B411 – Ron Brown Case study

T/O **0730 local (1030 UTC)**
Land **1230 local (1530 UTC)**

Mission Scientists: Steven Abel, Grant Allen, Hugh Coe, Alan Gadaian

Operating Area: South East Pacific Ocean, off the west coast of northern Chile, with ops area centred on 74° 46.8904'W, 19° 35.483'S

Waypoints:

ROMEO: 74° 46.8904'W, 19° 35.483'S

Radial to operate over point ROMEO: 125 and 305 degrees

Ron Brown Contact: Marine VHF RHB guards channel 13 and 16
Or on handheld radio on 1234.5

Sortie Objectives: To overfly the Ronald H Brown (RHB) cruise ship whilst on station at point ROMEO and perform a case study of the area; and intercompare radiometric and cloud instruments with measurements made by the Dornier and RHB.

Weather: High pressure system off shore capping a marine boundary layer with widespread Sc cloud. Near shore marine boundary layer winds from SSW.

Flight patterns:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6,000 ft amsl and begin 5-minute run to check instrumentation [11 min; T=0h 11 min]
2. Continue towards point ROMEO, beginning cycle below starting with immediate profile descent to 500ft below cloud top (1000 ft/min). [3 min; T=0h 14 min]
3. Perform 2 cycles consisting of:
 - a. 10-min straight/level leg in cloud,
 - b. Profile descent (1000 ft/min) to 500ft below cloud base,
 - c. 10-min straight/level leg sub-cloud,
 - d. profile descent (1000 ft/min) to 50ft,
 - e. i) On 1st cycle profile ascent (1000 ft/min) to 1000ft above cloud followed by immediate descent to 500ft below cloud top [cycle 30 min]
ii) On 2nd cycle profile ascent (1000 ft/min) to 500ft [cycle 26 min]

[T = 70 min]

4. Continue to point ROMEO to make contact with Ron Brown [5 min, T=75 min].

5. Reposition to start run at end of radial (35NM from ROMEO) at 100ft [15 min, T=90min]
6. SLR at 100ft for 70 NM [20 min, T=105 min]
7. Perform broken profile ascent to 500ft below cloud base (500 ft/min) to arrive at end point of radial (35NM along radial from ROMEO) [8min, T=113 min]
8. SLR at 500ft below cloud base for 70 NM [20 min, T=133 min]
9. Profile broken profile ascent to 500ft below cloud top (500 ft/min) to arrive at end point of radial (35NM along radial from ROMEO) [5min, T=118 min]
10. SLR at 500ft below cloud top for 70 NM [20 min, T=133 min]
11. Continue approx 2 more SLRs along radial both in cloud and sub-cloud as defined by mission scientist and a single profile to FL100 [T = 225 min]
12. Repeat outbound cycles (point 3) back towards Arica and land [T=300 min]

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode

Wet Neph – operated during all of 500ft runs

Dropsondes – 1 per degree of longitude on high level return between BETA and ALPHA

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Miss Scientist Notes:

Information:

Latest satellite image will be inserted prior to take-off

Mission Scientist Debrief 30/10/2008

Flight B411: Ron Brown case study flight

Steve Abel

Sortie Objectives: To overfly the Ronald H Brown (RHB) cruise ship whilst on station at the DART Buoy and to perform a case study of the area; and intercompare radiometric and cloud instruments with measurements made by the Dornier and RHB.

Cloud conditions: There was a sharp clearing in the cloud cover to the North of the DART Buoy as seen from the IR image below, with more uniform and thicker Sc to the South.

Mission profile

1. Profile ascent to 6000ft from Arica and 5 min SLR to check instrumentation. Inversion at 935 mbar.
2. Profile descent to 1000ft (cloud top 2900ft, base 2400ft).
3. 10min in cloud run at 2700 ft. Cloud was very diffuse and occasionally popped into clear gaps. 1300 cc-1 CN, 400 cc-1 CCN at S=0.2%
4. 10min run below cloud at 1900ft. AMS reported high sulphate of 3 ug m-3 with no organics.
5. 10 min run at 100 ft. 400 cc-1 CN, CCN dropped off along run from 200 – 50 cc-1. Similar drop in CO.
6. Ascent to 9000 ft – polluted layer at 830 mbar. CO increased to 60 ppb, O3 decreased to 30 ppb. Several other less polluted layers between 5000 and 9000 ft. CCN and CN see aerosol layers above cloud.

7. Profile descent to 1000 ft to make contact with Ron Brown. First overflight made at 11:37 UTC. Continued to work radial along 150 degrees at various altitudes along a track of 70NM centered on the Ron Brown. Runs consisted of;
8. In cloud run at 3400 ft, LWC ~ 0.3 gm-3, Cloud droplet conc ~150 cc-1, drizzle reported by 2DC and 2DS.
9. In cloud run at 3600 ft. RHB reports cloud base at 2800 ft. Similar cloud droplet conc and drizzle at start of run. Overpass of RHB at 12:06 Z. To the NW of the RHB the cloud thinned as shown in satellite image above.
10. Sub cloud run at 2000 ft. Possible signs of decoupled layer at NW end of run, perhaps preventing moisture transport to Sc above and resultant thinning of cloud. 300 cc-1 CN, 90 cc-1 CCN at S=0.2%. Drizzle evident at SE end of run where LWP is greater.
11. 100 ft run – some drizzle reaching surface at SE end of run. Good photo opportunity of RHB during fly pass. Thinning Sc again as continue run to NW.
12. Saw tooth leg profiling from 50 ft to 4800 ft. Boundary layer height increased from initial profile near coast to 895 mbar. As saw tooth from NW to SE cloud thickening and drizzle confined to SE part of leg. Higher aerosol concentrations to NW end.
13. In cloud run at 3500 ft with Dornier aircraft above at FL150. Cloud droplet conc ~ 300cc-1, MVD~17.5 um, LWC ~ 0.4 gm-3.
14. In cloud run at 3800 ft with Dornier above. Similar cloud microphysics.
15. In cloud run at 3500 ft with Dornier above. Cloud again thinned out to NW end of run. End of time overflying RHB.
16. In cloud run from RHB towards Arica at 3500ft. Cloud very diffuse with droplet concentrations ~ 100-150 cc-1. Flying in and out of cloud tops.
17. Profile ascent to FL010. O₃, CCN, CN and sulphate loading all dropped off at 6200ft. Moist layer just below FL010. Sc looked much more broken towards coast.
18. Profile descent to 50 ft. Pollution layer evident at 8000 ft – increase in CO and CN. Below cloud CCN and CN concentrations higher than at RHB.
19. 100 ft SLR towards coast. Gradual increase in CCN and sulphate as fly towards coast.
20. 2000 ft run towards coast showing further increases in CCN (300 cc-1) and sulphate (4 ug m-3). Hazy conditions and no change in CO or O₃, suggesting hydrated sulphate aerosol.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.411... Date ...30.11.08... Name ...Steve Abel... Page ...1... of ...11...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Weather at Arica airport
					Mainly clear skies with
					a few very small patches
					of cloud. Sat pic suggests
					clearance in Sc near coast.
					Looks hazy out to Sea
					Sea surface very flat.
					Odd bit of scud cloud at ~
					2000'? seen in front of w
103634					Sc formed near coast -
					thin layer - gaps in cloud
					to sea surface in places.
103739	P2 ↓	6000' → 1000'			Lots of structure in
					moisture profile above
					cloud. Cloud top 2900'
					Cloud base 2400'
					Some scuddy cloud below
					at 2000'
104242	P3 ↑	1000' - 2700'			Profile into cloud for
					10min SLR.
					Cloud base 2400'
104423	R1				Occasionally see glimpse
					of sea and sky - cloud is
					very thin and patchy
					LWC ~ 0.05 gm ⁻³

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...411... Date 30/10/08 Name STEVE ABEL Page 2 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
104843		2700'			Popped into gaps. Little bits of scudgy cloud below. 1300 CN CCN 400cm ³ at S=0.2%
105614	R3				As soon as pop down to 1900' CN drops to 500. Sulphate or VACC?
105800					Cloud appears starting again. Sc layer with scudgy looking cloud below.
105929					Descend 200' to go below cloud. Cloud is still very patchy and often into gaps
100600					CCN dropped off to normal level. Seems to be that peak aerosol was above MBL.
110619	Plot	profile to do		SLR at 100ft	
110926	R4				Start SLR at 100ft. Then Sc above. PCAIP reporting (cont) 2600 whereas CCN ~400. PCAIP has seen core dropping off as we go away from coast but need to have a good look at PCAIP data.

31 mins to Pen Brown

Mission Scientist's Log

Pen Down
160 hrs

Flight No B.4.11... Date 30/10/08.. Name STEVE ABEL Page 3 of 11...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					CN counts ~ 600 along run
					and stable. CCN dropped off from 200 to 50 cm ⁻³ along
					(S = 0.2%) run. CO also
111941	P6↑	111941	500'	→ 9000'	dropped off
					No decoupled cloud layer.
					Cloud base 2400'?
					Cloud top 3700'
					LWC peak ~ 0.15 gm ⁻³
					Manchester cloud physics
					CO and O ₂ increased above cloud but possible clear 1st
					~ 100m thick where humidity changes rapidly. Lot of turbulence above in this
					clear layer.
112841					So much more persistent to West as in satellite imagery
					→ Near coast decoupled layer and little SC
112920	P7↓	9000'		→ 1000'	→ where we are now no decoupled layer and SC.
					Core chem → lots of different layers in CO. from 55-65 ppb
					CCN rock being layers too
					as well in CN counts

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...411... Date ..30..110/08 Name ...STEVE ABEL Page ...4 of ...11.

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Cloud top 3700'
					Cloud base 3300'-3000'
					variable
					Core chem 1st elevated NOx
					seen ~1.5 ppt
					19,36.95 South } Ron Brown
					74,46.85 West }
114241					Cloud base 2800'
					Cloud top
114326	R6				In cloud run away from Ron Brown at 3600'
					10 minute run to take us to the end of radial
					LWC ~ 0.3 gm ⁻³
					FSSP ~ 170 cm ⁻³
					CDP ~ 170 cm ⁻³
					2DC seeing signs of light drizzle, as is CAP/2DS.
					Drop size peak ~ 17-18 μm
115321	run end.				Going to do 20 min leg back at 3600'
115559	R7	3700'			RWB Cloud base ~ 2800'
					CDP and FSSP giving similar concs as in R6
					Also similar drizzle amounts
120711					Very glimpse of sec surface ~ 1 sec! Drop in LWC.

D10 arriving about 12:55^z

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...411... Date ..30/10/08.. Name SEVE ABEL Page 5 of 11...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
120945					Very near cloud top → See glimpse of Sun occasionally.
121126					Cloud thinning toward end of run. Popping in and out of cloud. Drop in equivalent potential temp ~2-3°C as come out of cloud.
121535	R7	END			
121558	R7	down to 2600'			Cloud base 3200'
121938	R8	2600'			Run below cloud base. Possible signs of decoupled layer at end of previous run which may be consistent with thinning of Sc. As run as get decoupled layer prevents moisture getting into Sc. CN flatline ~ 3000cc ⁻¹ CCN ~ 90 cm ⁻³ at 0.2%
122640					Core chem noted that baseline has shifted on CO Probably ~ 800' below cloud base
123000					Cloud physics seeing bits of drizzle

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.4.1.1... Date ^{30/10/08} ~~30/10/08~~ Name ~~STEVE ABEL~~ ^{STEVE ABEL} Page 6 of 11...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
123108					Drizzle as pass over ship Clouds certainly producing more drizzle as clouds thicken up to SE.
123413					Period in humidity structure - 4 minutes. PCASP seems to be reading very high. 1000 cc ⁻¹ , 700 cc ⁻¹ without channel 1.
123919					As cloud thickens to SE cloud base dropping. Approx 300-400' below CB.
124202	P10	2000'		→ 100'	
124524	R9	100'			Some drizzle reaching the surface As passed Ron Brown good photos! Se starting to thin again as pass to NW past Ron Brown vertical velocity gradient ± 0.5 m ⁻¹ CN and CCN counts increasing as reaching NW end of run. No drizzle at this end PCASP 1300 cc ⁻¹ very strange! PCASP on CVI giving ~1000 cc ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 441... Date 30/10/08... Name STEVE ABEL... Page 7 of 11...

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
130512	P11↑	100 → 5000'			Aku Gachon noted 130300 large variation in TWC et Ascend for comfort break Cloud base 3200' Cloud top 3800' LWC ~ 0.1 gm ⁻³
132617	P12↓	5000' → 50'			Cloud top 3800' Cloud base 3200' Commencing saw tooth legs along track over Ron Brown to look at structure in sub- cloud layer. Profibs from 50' to just above cloud top.
133250	P13↑	50' → above cloud			Ship 1 knot on track of 150 from original position. Cloud base 2900' Cloud top 4200' Bit of turbulence above cloud top.
133716	P14↓	4400' → 50'			Cloud base ~ 2500' NW SE increased aerosol. KMS
134156			152°		Do 228 - 48 miles ahead of us Super adiabatic layer near surface

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...411... Date 30/11/08... Name STEVE ABEL... Page 8 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
134324	PIST	50' → 3500'			End profile in turn
					Cloud base ~ 2800 - 3000'
134726	END	Profile end	turn to		do SUR in cloud at 3500'
134836	R11	3500'			LWC ~ 0.25 gm ⁻³
					droplet radii ~ 10µm MVD ~ 17.5µm
					N ~ 300 cc ⁻³
					some drizzle.
					Dornier above us trailing
					just behind
					RHB says cloud base at 950m
135657					Cloud beginning to thin again and popping out at cloud base occasionally
					as pass ship - see in downward video
135952					Cloud variable at this altitude - still near cloud base
140241	P16A				
140531	R12	3800'			Cut run a bit shorter to ensure stay in thicker cloud and keep R228 above us. Start near cloud top level.
					MVD ~ 15µm N ~ 250 cc ⁻³
					dropping to 100 in gap. LWC ~ 0.2
141202					More vigorous cell

→ turbulence LWC increasing to 0.5 gm⁻³

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.4.1.1 Date 30/12/68 Name STEVE ABEL Page 9 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Increase in drizzle.
141636					Another big increase in LWC
142021	P17H	small			profile to 3500' for return leg in cloud.
142256	R13	3500'			Inbound run to Ron Brown
					DO-228 shortly follow us
					and then 146 and DO-228
					return to Arica.
					1938.05 S } Ron Brown
					074°46'32" W } ?
					Ron Brown radar now pointing
					down 220 radial to point in swell
142843					Just popped below cloud base
					Cloud by RHB more broken
					and thin.
143349	R14	3500'			Very thin cloud. Again
					see some scattered cloud below
					us at times. N ~ 100-150cc ⁻¹
143858					Cloud field very broken in
					places. and very thin
144112					Bit of turbulence ^{at} cloud ^{top} but not a lot
					top. Flying in and out of
					cloud top.
144409					Cloud very diffuse in patches
144455	P18↑				In profile cloud ^{cover} looks pretty
					extensive. Just very thin.

→ small LWP on satellite?

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.411... Date 30/10/68 Name STEVE ABEL Page 10 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					6200 ft O ₃ dropped off
					and CCN dropped off
					Sulphate loading down as well
					CN also dropping
					Interesting humidity change
					just above cloud. → dry slot?
					At 10000' in remnants of
					ci layer.
145341					Sc much more broken towards
					coast. Large gaps.
P19 ↓	145320	10000'	→ 50'		
					Ca sizeable layer at 10000'
					Very different than profile up.
					CN also increased
					Cloud top - 3300'
					Cloud base - 2600'
					Again very dry layer above
					cloud top and hydrolapre above
					that.
					0-2% S 150 CCN 500 CN compared to
				at. R16	60 CCN 300 CN
R10		100'	10min	SCR	Profile ^{shows} stable layer below cloud.
					q _v and MMR ↑ → moister as come towards
					coast, at 100' CCN 220/500.
					Gradual increase in CCN conc
					and sulphate as move towards coast.

P20 ↑ 111515
R16 151701
152454

100' → 2000'

2000' 10min SCR

Approaching thru cloud / dehydrated aerosol

Very hazy towards coast. sulphate still going up and CCN 300/650

Flight No. B411 Date 30/11/08 Name Steve Abel Page 11 of 14

IS2746 Small patchy cloud below and broken cloud above. ~~→ increase in ~~CCN~~ on~~
CCN is 300/1000 at 0.1% S.

P21↑ 2000' → 5000' . Again a dry layer above cloud top or possibly lag in GE?

R17 5000' Very patchy small scud clouds below us

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.411** Date **30/10/08** Name **G. ALLEN** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:06		0			Surface conditions: Unusually clear sky. Sat picture shows clear coastal shores out to Port buoy. 14°C (cooler than normal). Some mid-level wisps of cirrus overhead. DP = 7.21°C. No wind. Possible existence of haze layers out to sea.
10:25	P1A				Take off - Start of profile climb to 6000ft -
10:28					1st inversion at 935mb - lower than usual. T _{inversion} = 17.3°C. - warmer than surface.
10:32					Start of SIC run at 6000ft -
10:37	P2A				End of run, start of descent to below cloud profile cycle -
10:42	P3A				Start of profile climb -
10:45					In-cloud at 919mb - 10°C. Clouds v. thin and diffuse. Had to stay in it -
10:55	P4A				Profile descent to 1700ft - CCN reporting high aerosol than on flight so far.
10:57					AMS reporting 3 µg/m ³ SO ₄ , but low organics -
11:06	P5A				Descent to 100ft to look for aerosol layer.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B411** Date **30/10/08** Name **G. ALLEN** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:09	R4	50 ft			Run at 100ft above cloud look for aerosol. NO sign of it!
11:11					PCASP reporting probe problem - CN ~ 400 /cc CCN ~ 50 /cc.
11:19	P6T				Profile ascent from 50ft to 1000ft. 1000ft/min.
11:25					CO $\rightarrow$ to 60 ppbv, O ₃ $\leftarrow$ to 30 ppbv. - Thin polluted layer at around 830 mb.
11:30					Several layers between 5000 and 10000 ft!
11:37	R5	900ft			Run at 981 mb. 500ft below cloud. Over Ron Brown. 34
11:41	P8T				Profile climb for Ron Brown overpass. NO sign of any pollution affecting the area. Thick Sc deck overhead though.
11:43	R6	3400ft	SE		S/L 20-min run at 3400ft. FSS ₅₀ > 100, Drizzle reported.
11:59	R7	3600ft	NW	NW	S/L 20 min run at 3600ft. Ron Brown reporting height of 2800 ft for cloud base.
12:05					Dornier 1hr away.
12:06:30					Over Ron Brown.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B411**..... Date **30/10/03**..... Name **G. ALLEN**..... Page **3** of **4**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:18	P96				Descent to 2000ft.
					Reported that Dornier going via Alpha.
12:19	R8	2000ft.	SE		39 miles from RHB - 800ft below cloud base.
12:43	P06				Down to 100ft.
12:45	R9	100ft.	NW		100ft.
13:05	P41				
13:26	P126		SE		Descent and start of sawtooth peaking pattern.
					A polluted air mass was present above cloud on the extended run.
					No superadiabatic layers seen on first profile.
					BL height increased. In cloud run, still below inversion at 895mb, 6.14°C.
13:49	R10				3500ft SLR run.
					Dornier tracking just behind and above us.
					Cap 20 Jan 300/100. 04:00 LWC.
					Some drizzle. (950m cloud base.)
14:02					Dornier deviated from flight plan and flew between 205 and RHB.

but didn't extend for the NW leg of the landing RHB.

VOCALS BAe-146 Instrument status Report

Date of report(UTC): 2008/10/30 18:30

Author of report: Steve Abel

Submitted at(UTC): 2008/10/30 18:35

Remaining flight hours: 45

General Comments:

After Ron Brown mission on 30/10/2008

INSTRUMENTS / SYSTEMS STATUS

 = no report

Meteorology / Navigation

1.	GPS (Patch)	Comment:	
2.	GPS (Cruciform)	Comment:	
3.	Temperature/Pressure	Comment:	
4.	Water Vapor (Hygrometer)	Comment:	
5.	Turbulence Probe	Comment:	
6.	Altitude (RadarAlt)	Comment:	
7.	Doppler Radar	Comment:	
8.	Dropsonde (AVAPS)	Comment:	

Radiation

9.	Broadband Radiometer (BBR)	Comment:	
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10.	Spectral Radiometer (ARIES)	Comment:	
11.	In-flight Microwave Obs System (DEIMOS)	Comment:	
12.	Microwave Radiometer Scanning System (MARSS)	Comment:	
13.	Shortwave Spectrometer (SWS)	Comment:	
14.	Spectral Irradiance (SHIM)	Comment:	lower SHIMS not working
15.	Heimann Downward-facing Radiometer	Comment:	

Chemistry

16.	Ozone (CAMP 2B)	Comment:	
17.	NO _x	Comment:	
18.	CO (AL5002)	Comment:	
19.	SO ₂ (TECO 43C)	Comment:	
20.	Sample Bottles (WAS)	Comment:	
21.	CH ₄ /CO ₂ (NIR-TDLAS)	Comment:	
22.	PAN (GC)	Comment:	not operated
23.	Volatile Aerosol Composition (VACC)	Comment:	
24.	CH ₄ /N ₂ O (1C-TDLAS)	Comment:	

Cloud Physics and Aerosol

25.	Liquid and Total water probe	Comment:	
26.	LWC (Johnson Williams)	Comment:	
27.	TWC	Comment:	
28.	FFSSP	Comment:	
29.	2D-C	Comment:	
30.	PCASP	Comment:	possible noise in ch 1
31.	Small Ice Detector (SID-2)	Comment:	
32.	Cloud and Precipitation Imager (CIP-15)	Comment:	
33.	Cloud Droplet Probe (CDP)	Comment:	
34.	Condensation Nucleus Counter (CNC)	Comment:	
35.	Cloud Condensation Nuclei Spectrometer (CCNc)	Comment:	
36.	Fluorescence water vapour sensor (FWVS)	Comment:	
37.	Dry Nephelometer	Comment:	
38.	Wet Nephelometer	Comment:	some data recording problems
39.	Black Carbon (PSAP)	Comment:	
40.	Filters	Comment:	
41.	Aerosol Mass Spectrometer (AMS)	Comment:	
42.	Counter-flow virtual Impactor (CVI)	Comment:	

43.	2-D Imaging Probe (SPEC-2D-S-128H)	Comment:	
44.	CAPS	Comment:	
45.	Single Particle Soot Photometer (SP-2)	Comment:	was not optimised
46.	Fine-mode Aerosol Spectrometer (UHSAS)	Comment:	
47.	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS)	Comment:	
48.	Ultrafine particle counter 1 (LP-WUCPC-1)	Comment:	
49.	Ultrafine particle counter 2 (LP-WUCPC-2)	Comment:	

Other

50.	SATCOM C	Comment:	
51.	SATCOM H	Comment:	
52.	Up, Down, Front, Rear Digital Imagery	Comment:	

[prev](#) | [next](#)

 [Back to VOCALS Field Catalog](#) | [edit](#) | [delete](#)

comments : gstoss at ucar.edu

Chemistry Log

Date: 30/10/08

Flight: B410

Operator: KT.

Preflight

CO, O₃, NO_x, SO₂ fitted + operated

No. ? or x	Location	Action	Comments
Gases			
1	☒ CO2/Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
2	☒ CO2/Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	180
3	☒ CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	
4	☒ CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	45
5	☒ Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 2.5 bar	30
6	☒ Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	
Flows			
7	☒ Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 0.7 LPM on both channels	
8	☒ NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	☒ NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	☒ CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	☒ CO cell pressure	~ 7.5 bar	
12	☒ CO Pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	
Zeros			
13	☒ Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	☒ NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	☒ CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	
Other			
16	☒ Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
17	☒ HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
18	☒ CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	Manual valve herm
TDLAS			
19	☒ 230V	230V power breakers on	
20	☒ 28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
21	☒ Laptop	On and software working	
22	☒ Data	Being saved to correct directories	
Post Flight			
Switch off			
1	☒ CO	Switch off instrument	
2	☒ Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	☒ NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	☒ Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	☒ Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
Gases (note pressures)			
6	☒ CO2/Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	180
7	☒ CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	45
8	☒ Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	30
Driers			
9	☒ Small drier	Change if spent	
10	☒ Large drier	Change if spent	
TDLAS			
11	☒ Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	☒ Laptop	Shut down	
13	☒ Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
Log			
14	☒ Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	☒ Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	☒ TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

Chemistry Log

In flight B411

CO calibrations only need carrying out when the lamp temperature changes, if unsure perform a quick cal first.

During each CO calibration check Ozone and NOx flows are similar to those observed pre-flight

Time	Flight level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Count (Hz)	Lamp Temp (deg C)	Cell Pressure (Torr)
10:20	Tascy	98.93	310.14	30683	35.48	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO				
11:10	500FT	Manual valve turns		30000	35.87	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
11:39	500FT	Manual valve turns		29600	36.53	7.54
Time	Flight level	CO				
12:20	F2078	Manual valve turns		29300	37.33	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO				
13:00	100FT	Manual valve turns		29200	37.64	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO				
13:59	F2038	Manual valve turns		29000	37.99	7.53
Time	Flight level	CO				
15:06	100FT	Manual valve turns		29000	38.26	7.52
Time	Flight level	CO				

In flight comments
<p style="font-size: 1.2em; font-family: cursive;">Large drier replaced post B410</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 411

Date: 30/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
10:28:13	5800	0.08	0													FL020	
10:29:20	4500	0.07														FL030	
10:30:40	1700	0.07														FL040	
10:31:18	2400	0.08														FL050	
10:32:20	1500	0.07														End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1@ FL060	
10:33:00	1300	0.07															
10:35:00	1200	0.07															
10:37:00	1300	0.07															
10:37:39																End of Run 1 @ Start Profile 2	
10:38:45	780	0.07														FL050	
10:39:53	1900	0.07														FL040	
10:40:41	3300	0.07														FL030	
10:41:42	4100	0.08														FL020	
10:42:47	4000	0.08														End of P2 & Start profile 3 from FL010	
10:44:09	4000	0.08	656													FL020	
10:45:00	4600	0.10	867			3	75	300	10				250	12	0.15	12	End of Profile & Start Run 2 @ 2700'
10:47:00	4400	0.08	3370					200	10				250	11	0.15	12	
10:49:00	3600	0.08	3600														
10:51:00	4000	0.08	3638														
10:53:00	3900	0.08	3680														
10:55:02																	End of Run 2 & Start Profile 4
10:55:51	3800	0.08															FL020
10:56:10																	End of Profile 4 & Start Run 3 @ FL018
10:57:00	4000	0.08															
10:59:00	3600	0.08	3696														
11:01:00	3669	0.08	3714														
11:03:00	3500	0.08	3734														
11:05:00	3200	0.08															
11:06:12																	End of Run 3 & Start Profile 5
11:07:04	2400	0.08	3735														FL010
11:09:26																	End of Profile 5 & Start Run 4 @ 100'
11:10:00	2300	0.07															
11:12:00	2000	0.07															
11:14:00	1800	0.07															
11:16:00	1700	0.07															
11:18:00	1300	0.08															
11:19:16																	End of Run 4
11:19:50	1300	0.08															Start Profile 6 from 50'
11:21:00	1000	0.08															FL010
11:21:58	1000	0.07															FL020
11:22:59	9200	0.10	3772			11	75	200	20				120	20	0.4	12	FL030
11:24:10	900	0.07	3780														FL040
11:25:16	250	0.07															FL050

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 411

Date: 30/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:26:21	200	0.08	3780													FL060	
11:27:26	60	0.08														FL070	
11:28:32	170	0.07														FL080	
11:29:17	150	0.07														End of Profile 6 & Start P7 @ FL090	
11:30:22	300	0.08														FL080	
11:31:20	90	0.09														FL070	
11:32:14	70	0.08														FL060	
11:33:04	90	0.08														FL050	
11:33:54	600	0.08														FL040	
11:34:47	700	0.09	3807			1	100								12	FL030	
11:35:52	1100	0.08														FL020	
11:37:09																End of Profile 7 @ 1000'	
11:38:00	1300	0.07															
11:40:30																End of Run & Start Profile 8	
11:41:55	1140	0.07				1										FL020	
11:43:24																End of P8 & Start Run 6 @ FL033	
11:44:00	9000	0.15	4026			25	200	200	20			0.6	140	20	0.5	1	
11:46:00	6700	0.16	4323			50	200	120	20				120	18	0.5	1	
11:48:00	6800	0.16	4631			15	250	200	19			0.5	120	18	0.3	1	
11:50:00	5500	0.17	4874			30	300	100	18			0.45	120	18	0.3	1	
11:52:00	8000	0.16	5081			30	350	150	18			0.4	130	19	0.3	1	
11:53:20																End of Run	
11:56:02																Start Run 7 @ 3600'	
11:57:00	13000	0.15	5800			70	350	150	20			0.6	120	21	0.5	1	
11:59:00	8700	0.16	6034			15	300	200	20			0.5	120	20	0.5	1	
12:01:00	8700	0.16	6480			35	300	120	20			0.5	130	20	0.5	1	
12:03:00	5500	0.16	6681			35	200	100	20			0.5	120	20	0.5	1	
12:05:00	15000	0.15	7065			30	200	200	19			0.5	140	18	0.5	1	
12:07:00	2300	0.14	7196			30	200	200	17			0.75	125	17	0.3	1	
12:09:00	5500	0.15	7433			12	75	175	18			0.5	150	19	0.5	12	
12:11:00	9000	0.15	7567			2	75	170	17			0.2	100	11	0.1	12	
12:13:00	900	0.10	7629			8	75	100	12			0.2	50	14	0.1	12	
12:15:00	2900	0.14	7877			20	175										
12:15:36																End of Run 7	
12:15:58																Start Profile 9	
12:19:24																End of Profile @ 2000'	
12:19:38																	
12:20:00	1300	0.08	7928														
12:22:00	1200	0.08															
12:24:00	1240	0.08															
12:26:00	1400	0.08															
12:28:00	1250	0.08	7929														
12:30:00	1200	0.08															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 411

Date: 30/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:32:00	1200	0.08	7930			5	600								1		
12:34:00	1000	0.08															
12:36:00	900	0.08	7931			1	300								1		
12:38:00	1000	0.08															
12:40:00	1300	0.08	7932			1	400								1		
12:42:03																End of Run & Start Profile 10	
12:45:18																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 8 @ 100'	
12:46:00	1300	0.08	7933														
12:48:00	1390	0.07															
12:50:00	1070	0.08															
12:52:00	1000	0.07															
12:54:00	1000	0.08															
12:56:00	1000	0.07	7934														
12:58:00	1050	0.07															
13:00:00	1300	0.07															
13:02:00	1200	0.08															
13:04:00	1200	0.07															
13:05:13																End of Run 9 & Start Profile 11	
13:06:21	1100	0.08	7935													FL010	
13:07:25	1000	0.08														FL020	
13:08:34	1100	0.08	7964													FL030	
13:09:39	1170	0.07	8020													FL040	
13:10:17	1900	0.07	8024													FL050	
13:24:36																Start Run 10 @ FL050	
13:25:00	760	0.07															
13:26:14																End of Run 10 & Start Profile 12	
13:27:15	875	0.07														FL040	
13:28:15	950	0.08	8038													FL030	
13:29:08	990	0.07														FL020	
13:29:59	1015	0.08														FL010	
13:31:41	1150	0.08														End of P12 & Start Profile 13 @ 50'	
13:34:58	1000	0.08														FL010	
13:34:58	800	0.08														FL020	
13:35:48	2600	0.10														FL030	
13:36:48	500	0.08														FL040	
13:37:18	540	0.08														End of P13 & Start P14 @ FL042	
13:37:37	600	0.09														FL040	
13:38:48	800	0.10	8185													FL030	
13:39:40	1250	0.08														FL020	
13:40:31	1350	0.08														FL010	
13:43:11	1340	0.08														End of Profile 14 & Start P15 from 50'	
13:44:27	1100	0.07	8186													FL010	
13:45:28	1070	0.07														FL020	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 411

Date: 30/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
13:46:33	1600	0.11	8227													FL030	
13:47:26																End of Profile 15 @ FL033	
13:48:34																Start Run 11 @ 3500'	
13:49:00	6000	0.16	8580			55	325	200	20			0.1	140	18	0.3	1	
13:51:00	7500	0.15	8748			30	125	200	20			0.3	120	20	0.6	12	
13:53:00	800	0.12	8942			10	125	200	15			0.2	120	16	0.5	12	
13:55:00	1800	0.14	9075			35	225	180	15			0.3	120	22	0.4	1	
13:57:00	850	0.09	9254			5	150	100	10				75	15	0.04	1	
13:59:00	1200	0.11	9318			16	150	100	17				100	10	0.05	1	
14:01:00	670	0.09	9433			5	125	200	17				75				
14:02:08																End of Run	
14:02:35																Start Profile 16	
14:04:00																End of Profile 16	
12:05:41																Start Run 12 @ FL036	
12:06:00	3000	0.16	9730			35	150	100	20				100	15	0.1	12	
12:08:00	5700	0.14	9874			6	100	100	20				110	17.5	0.2	12	
12:10:00	2700	0.14	10111			14	100	100	18				100	20	0.6	1	
12:12:00	5200	0.14	10251			15	200	100	22				125	20	0.6	1	
14:14:00	3000	0.15	10493			20	100	110	10				120	20	0.2	1	
14:16:00	6700	0.15	10652			30	225	140	22				140	20	0.2	1	
14:18:00	25400	0.14	10963			40	150	105	22				120	18	0.2	1	
14:20:23																End of Run 12 & Start Profile 17	
14:20:51																End of Profile 17 @ FL033	
14:22:55																Start Run 13 @ 3500'	
14:23:00	8300	0.16	11570			80	225	120	15				120	20	0.6	1	
14:25:00	11694	0.15	11753			20	225	200	20				120	20	0.4	1	
14:27:00	11904	0.14	11924			60	175	170	20				140	20	0.4	1	
14:29:00	2000	0.11	12060			4	100	170	20				25	10	0.05	12	
14:31:00	5000	0.14	12100			20	150	100	20				125	22	0.8	1	
14:32:47																End of Run 13	
14:33:46																Start Run 14 @ 3500'	
14:34:00	3000	0.14	12407			5	125	100	18				100	12	0.05	12	
14:36:00	2400	0.10	12450			3	125	100	17				100	18	0.3	12	
14:38:00	1000	0.08	12515														
14:40:00	1500	0.10	12540			3	75	100	17				125	14	0.15	12	
14:42:00	1260	0.08	12500														
14:44:00	1000	0.08	12664														
14:44:49																End of Run 14 & Start Profile 18	
14:45:30	1250	0.7	12694													FL040	
14:46:26	800	0.07														FL050	
14:47:16	125	0.08														FL060	
14:48:10	80	0.07														FL070	
14:48:59	130	0.08														FL080	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 411

Date: 30/10/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:45:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 5 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
14:50:10	160	0.07	12694													FL090	
14:51:14																End of Profile 14 & Start Run 15 @ FL100	
14:52:00	90	0.08															
14:53:10																Start Profile 15 from FL100	
14:54:15	110	0.07														FL090	
14:55:05	240	0.07														FL080	
14:55:56	190	0.07														FL070	
14:56:43	350	0.07														FL060	
14:57:38	1200	0.07														FL050	
14:58:30	1200	0.07														FL040	
14:59:59	1660	0.08	12697													FL030	
15:01:04	2100	0.08														FL020	
15:02:18	2200	0.08														FL010	
15:04:55	2800	0.08														End of Profile 15 @ 50'	
15:05:15																Start Run 15 @ 100'	
15:06:00	2700	0.08															
15:08:00	2800	0.08															
15:10:00	3000	0.08															
15:12:00	3000	0.08															
15:14:00	3060	0.08															
15:15:11																End of Run 15 Start Profile 16	
15:16:12	2900	0.08	12698													FL010	
15:16:58																End of Run 15 & Start Run 16 @ 2000'	
15:17:00	2800	0.08															
15:19:00	3000	0.08															
15:21:00	3500	0.08															
15:23:00	4000	0.08															
15:25:00	4000	0.08															
15:27:00	4900	0.08	12699														
15:28:05																End of Run 16 & Start Profile 17	
15:29:19	3500	0.07														FL030	
15:30:26	1500	0.08														FL040	
15:31:17																End of Profile & Start Run 17 @ 5000'	
15:32:00	1400	0.08															
15:34:00	1200	0.08															
15:36:30																End of Run	
PCASP Concentrations considered high and PCASP channel 1 seems very high																	
Bead calibration on Manchester FFSSP and CDP																	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8.4V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.2V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -2.0V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.6V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 0.7CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CVI log

10/30/08 10:33:47 AM
10/30/08 10:34:00 AM
10/30/08 10:35:27 AM hygro zero done at start of run 1
10/30/08 10:35:49 AM hygro back to sample, still in counterflow mode.
10/30/08 10:37:28 AM
10/30/08 10:38:34 AM left in counter flow mode ready for decent into cloud
10/30/08 10:40:10 AM AMS and SP2 on
10/30/08 10:40:33 AM AMS and SP2 on cf to 3.8
10/30/08 10:40:43 AM cloud
10/30/08 10:41:35 AM NOTE INC flow used to give cpc flow wjich is hard coded for zero at present
10/30/08 10:42:20 AM below cloud, leave in cf mode as we will be heading back up.
10/30/08 10:44:28 AM not good zero below cloud
10/30/08 10:44:38 AM in cloud
10/30/08 10:51:21 AM just above cloud tops
10/30/08 10:55:26 AM reasonable zero at end of cloud free cloud run.
10/30/08 10:56:34 AM Manchester back to rosemounts
10/30/08 10:56:50 AM CF off aerosol mode
10/30/08 10:58:02 AM CF off aerosol mode
10/30/08 11:07:13 AM hygro very noisy in aerosol mode
10/30/08 11:16:50 AM PCSP flow tweeked
10/30/08 11:23:24 AM cloud, in aerosol mode! too late.
10/30/08 11:23:34 AM out of cloud
10/30/08 11:27:14 AM hygro going negative, outside air drier than counter flow
10/30/08 11:34:04 AM cf mode for cloud penetration
10/30/08 11:35:09 AM cf off below cloud
10/30/08 11:41:07 AM cf mode on for cloud run
10/30/08 11:41:20 AM cf mode on for cloud run
10/30/08 11:42:35 AM base of cloud
10/30/08 11:42:42 AM cloud
10/30/08 12:07:27 PM broken cloud
10/30/08 12:11:14 PM breaking through cloud tops
10/30/08 12:16:32 PM leave in cf mode for profile down, out of cloud, check zero
10/30/08 12:16:49 PM Manchester to rosemounts
10/30/08 12:18:11 PM good zero.
10/30/08 12:18:24 PM hygro at zero, good.
10/30/08 12:18:56 PM cf mode off aerosol mode
10/30/08 12:30:12 PM possible drizzle
10/30/08 12:30:23 PM drizzle confirmed
10/30/08 12:44:22 PM drizzle
10/30/08 1:08:39 PM leave in aerosol mode for profile through cloud.
10/30/08 1:08:51 PM cloud
10/30/08 1:26:29 PM pofile downs through thin broken cloud
10/30/08 1:33:23 PM
10/30/08 1:33:31 PM
10/30/08 1:35:46 PM cloud
10/30/08 1:37:55 PM cloud
10/30/08 1:38:54 PM out of cloud.
10/30/08 1:44:29 PM
10/30/08 1:44:33 PM
10/30/08 1:44:48 PM cf on ready for cloud run
10/30/08 1:45:07 PM manchester switched to CVI
10/30/08 1:46:14 PM cloud base
10/30/08 2:03:35 PM out of cloud, heading back to ship, leave in CVI mode for now
10/30/08 2:04:38 PM cloud tops
10/30/08 2:05:44 PM in cloud run 12
10/30/08 2:07:53 PM just skimming cloud tops
10/30/08 2:12:23 PM hygro giving much less water than others. Manchester giving 0.2gm/m3
10/30/08 2:14:08 PM hygro giving much less water than others. Manchester giving 0.2gm/m3.
10/30/08 2:14:44 PM cvi hygro see's about half what manchesters see.
10/30/08 2:34:12 PM only just in cloud base
10/30/08 2:38:54 PM clear patch
10/30/08 2:42:07 PM cloud tops
10/30/08 2:45:25 PM manchester to rosemounts
10/30/08 2:46:16 PM leave in cf mode for mo

10/30/08 2:46:40 PM pretty good zero
10/30/08 2:47:04 PM cf off, aerosol mode
10/30/08 2:56:31 PM big peaks in hygro and particles, probably old cirrus layer.
10/30/08 2:59:54 PM clouds
10/30/08 3:26:51 PM scattered cloud about and hazy
10/30/08 3:54:58 PM hygro to zero

ARIES flight log

Flight: B111

page 1 of 1

Date: 30/Oct/2008 Operator(s): S. Rogers

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc/Notes: VOCALS 20degS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
09 05 30	On the ground		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin script.
10 20 24	Take off						
10 32 37	R1		NZ	O	71	31	NadZenLongRun 30 sec End 10.38
10 37 39	EOR ↓		—	C	71	31	
10 56 14	R3 1900ft		NZ	O	71	31	NadZenLongRun 30 sec. In aerosol? ^{clear.}
10 59 20	↓ 1700ft				71	31	Dropping slightly to go under cloud
11 06 20	↓ EOR			C			
11 09 35	R4 100ft		NZ	O	70	31	NadZenLongRun 30 sec.
11 19 41	EOR ↑			C	71	31	
11 37			NZ	O	71	30	NadZenLongRun 30 sec. script.
11 39				O	71	31	Banking
11 40 52	↑		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin script
12 19 38	R5 200ft		NZ	O	71	30	NadZenLongRun 30 sec.
~ 12 31							Above "Ron Brown"
12 42	EOR ↓		—	C	71	31	
12 44 15			CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin
12 45 39	100ft	240x1	Z	O	71	31	Zenith
12 47 56	"		N	C	71	31	NadirLongRun 3 min
13 02 05	"	240x1	Z	O	71	31	Zenith
13 04 09	"		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin. script
13 24	???		N	C	71	31	NadirLongRun 30 min script <u>Aborted</u> . ↓
13 56			N	C	71	31	— " — in cloud.
14 02	EOR						Profile manoeuvre.
14 05 31	R12		N	C	71	31	... still NadirLongRun 3 min
14 20 28	EOR ↓		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin script
14 23 00			N	C	71	30	NadirLongRun 3 min. script
14 32	EOR						
14 33			N	C	71	31	NadirLongRun 3 min
14 44 48	EOR ↑		CH	C	71	31	ColdHotMin
15 05	100 ft.		N	C	71	31	NadirLongRun 3 min Broken Cu above
15 16 01	2000 ft.		ZN	O	71	31	NadZenLongRun 30 sec. Shadows directly below
15 31	5000		ZN	O	71	31	— " —

END

B411_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

08:39:54.73 --- - - - -
08:39:54.73 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
08:39:54.73 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn /
    Period / tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
08:39:54.73 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B411
08:39:54.73 --- - - - -
08:40:03.45 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:40:06.24 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:40:06.80 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
08:40:10.70 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to
    100ms.
08:40:16.15 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to
    100ms.
08:40:19.14 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:40:20.51 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:40:20.62 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to
    100ms.
08:40:21.97 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
08:40:24.02 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:40:29.42 SWS - - 100 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    100ms.
08:40:29.42 SWS - - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    100ms.
08:40:34.06 USH - - 600 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
08:40:35.26 USH - - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
08:40:39.25 SWS - - 400 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to
    400ms.
08:40:39.25 SWS - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 100ms to
    400ms.
08:40:42.01 USH - - 400 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to
    400ms.
08:40:42.01 USH - - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 600ms to
    400ms.
08:40:43.80 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
08:40:47.44 LSH - - 600 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
08:40:47.45 LSH - - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to
    600ms.
08:40:49.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:40:49.98 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:40:49.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:41:35.40 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:41:35.43 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:41:35.59 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:41:36.43 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
08:41:39.84 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:41:40.25 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
08:41:42.15 USH - - - - Idling
08:41:42.18 SWS - - - - Idling
08:41:42.89 LSH - - - - Idling
08:42:00.96 --- - - - - *** 21 deg
08:45:05.41 --- - - - - *** 20 deg
08:47:54.44 --- - - - - *** 19 deg
08:50:59.75 --- - - - - *** 18 deg
08:54:31.28 --- - - - - *** 17 deg
08:57:14.84 --- - - - - *** 16 deg
09:00:50.41 --- - - - - *** 15 deg
09:00:58.19 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:00:58.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:00:58.20 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

09:01:06.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:07.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:07.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:11.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:11.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:13.37	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:01:13.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:01:21.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:01:22.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:03:38.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
09:08:56.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
09:13:42.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 drg
09:15:28.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
09:19:50.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
09:53:02.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:02.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:02.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:08.87	SWS	-	-	600	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
09:53:08.87	SWS	-	-	-	600	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
09:53:14.09	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
09:53:19.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:23.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:27.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:27.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:27.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:32.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:34.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:34.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:53:34.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
09:53:52.99	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
09:53:53.00	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
09:53:56.31	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 100ms.
09:53:56.32	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 100ms.
09:53:58.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:58.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:58.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:53:59.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:54:00.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:54:01.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:54:01.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:54:03.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:54:03.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:54:04.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:22.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:02:51.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:06:33.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:11:06.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:11:38.53	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:11:38.54	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
10:11:40.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:41.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:42.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:43.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:47.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:48.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:11:49.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:51.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:11.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:11.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:11.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:22.94	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 100.000
10:12:24.07	SWS	99.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:12:26.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:29.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:00.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:16:27.57	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:16:33.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:33.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:33.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:35.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:16:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:39.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:41.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:43.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:43.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:43.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:16:44.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:45.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:16:51.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:25:57.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:26:53.89	SWS	100.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:26:55.03	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:26:56.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:56.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:57.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:58.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:58.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:03.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:27:20.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
10:29:22.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:23.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:25.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:26.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:29.17	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:29:29.17	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:29:30.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:31.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:29:32.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:29:33.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:52.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:31:55.83	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:31:59.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:59.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:31:59.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:32:00.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:00.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:32:06.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:33:19.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
10:34:37.17	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 50ms.
10:34:37.19	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 50ms.
10:34:39.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:34:39.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:34:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:43.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.

10:34:51.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:51.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:51.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:51.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:34:56.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:34:57.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:02.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:02.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:02.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:02.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:36:03.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:36:03.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:03.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:05.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:05.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:05.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:06.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:36:07.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:07.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:04.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:39:01.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:40:55.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
10:41:06.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:08.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:12.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:13.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:18.50	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:43:23.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:23.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:23.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:43:23.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:43:24.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:24.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:43:25.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:27.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:27.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:27.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:31.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:41.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:41.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:41.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:41.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:44:42.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:42.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:42.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:47.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:47.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:47.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:47.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:44:48.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:48.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:44:48.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:50.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:50.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:50.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:44:50.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:44:51.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:51.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:44:51.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

10:45:02.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:45:15.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
10:45:31.15	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
10:45:31.16	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 30ms.
10:45:36.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:36.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:47.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:47.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:47.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:48.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:45:48.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:48.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:48.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:52.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:52.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:52.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:53.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:45:53.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:53.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:53.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:55.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:55.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:55.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:56.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:45:56.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:57.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:57.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:57.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:57.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:58.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:45:58.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:59.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:59.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:45:59.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:00.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:00.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:00.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:01.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:01.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:01.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:46:17.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:17.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:17.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:20.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:20.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:22.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:46:23.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:46:48.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
10:48:01.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:01.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:01.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:02.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:48:02.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:48:02.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:02.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:48:03.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:48:20.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:35.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

10:50:36.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:36.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:50:38.67	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:50:40.35	SWS	170.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:50:42.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:42.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:50:42.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:24.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:24.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:24.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:52:26.33	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:52:28.00	SWS	-2.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:52:28.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:28.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:52:28.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:03.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** not much cloud around so doing some aerosol work
10:53:25.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 degree
10:53:45.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** mainly using zenith views for aerosol work
10:53:54.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:54.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:54.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:54.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
10:53:55.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:55.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:55.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:14.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
10:56:25.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3
11:00:19.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:02:07.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:07:41.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:41.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:41.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:41.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:49.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:49.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:49.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:49.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:07:49.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:50.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:51.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:51.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:51.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:52.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:52.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:52.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:54.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:54.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:54.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:07:54.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:07:54.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:55.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:07:55.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:08:05.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:05.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:05.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:37.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 100 ft
11:10:09.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:09.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

11:10:09.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:10:12.15	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:10:13.87	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:10:16.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:16.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:10:16.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:04.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:04.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:04.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:11:06.92	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:11:08.64	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:11:12.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:12.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:12.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:17.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:17.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:17.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:11:17.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:11:18.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:18.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:11:18.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:47.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:48.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:51.69	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:15:51.70	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:15:53.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:54.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:15:55.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:15:56.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:16:24.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** patchy cloud above
11:17:17.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:17.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:17.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:34.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:34.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:34.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:35.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:17:35.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:35.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:35.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:36.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:36.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:36.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:37.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:38.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:38.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:39.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:39.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:39.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:17:40.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:40.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:40.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:17:51.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:51.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:17:51.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:39.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:18:39.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:18:39.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:18:41.93	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:18:43.64	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

11:18:47.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:47.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:18:47.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:19:42.82	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:19:44.54	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:19:57.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 6 from 50 ft
11:22:44.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** still 15 deg
11:23:12.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
11:23:28.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud
11:23:36.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 37000
11:25:30.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:30.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:30.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:25:30.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:26:07.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:07.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:07.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:29:33.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of climb and start of profile descent
11:29:49.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p 6 and atart of p 7
11:31:43.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:34:14.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
11:34:43.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud
11:42:54.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:54.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:54.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:55.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:42:55.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:55.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:56.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:11.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
11:43:21.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of in coud run
11:43:38.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 6
11:44:10.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:45:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:34.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:34.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:45:37.29	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:45:39.02	SWS	173.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:45:44.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:44.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:44.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:09.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:09.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:09.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:47:12.30	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:47:14.03	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:47:15.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:15.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:15.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:08.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:53:24.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:24.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:24.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:29.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:29.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:29.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:30.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:53:30.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:31.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:31.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:32.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:53:32.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:32.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:33.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:33.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:33.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:34.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:34.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:53:35.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:35.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:35.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:42.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:42.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:42.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:00.20	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:54:01.94	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:55:53.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:56:01.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
11:56:11.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 7
11:57:22.58	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:57:24.26	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:59:54.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:01:06.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:01:07.86	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:02:32.03	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:02:33.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:06:42.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:07:21.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:07:23.02	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:08:48.59	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:08:50.30	SWS	-3.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:09:15.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:16.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:16.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:24.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:24.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:24.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:24.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:09:25.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:25.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:25.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:26.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:26.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:26.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:27.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:28.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:28.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:29.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:29.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:29.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:30.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:30.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:30.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:09:43.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:43.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:43.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:25.91	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:10:27.65	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:12:57.47	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:12:59.18	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:13:26.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** skimming cloud base
12:13:49.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:15:37.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run

```

12:16:09.65 --- - - - - *** profile descent to 2000 ft p9
12:19:42.69 --- - - - - *** run
12:20:02.08 --- - - - - *** run 8 below cloud at 2000 ft
12:20:15.06 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:20:16.80 SWS 173.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:21:04.70 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:21:06.44 SWS -5.7 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:32:06.16 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
12:33:29.46 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:33:31.26 SWS 173.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:35:10.32 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:35:12.11 SWS -5.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:37:36.28 --- - - - - *** 12 dwg
12:41:15.77 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:15.82 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:15.84 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:16.32 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
12:41:16.58 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:41:17.05 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:41:17.11 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:41:47.39 SWS - - - - Idling
12:41:47.45 USH - - - - Idling
12:41:47.48 LSH - - - - Idling
12:41:55.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:55.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:55.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:56.15 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
12:41:56.45 USH - - - - Idling
12:41:56.84 SWS - - - - Idling
12:41:56.87 LSH - - - - Idling
12:41:58.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:58.34 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:58.36 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:41:59.11 SWS - - - - Idling
12:41:59.52 LSH - - - - Idling
12:41:59.53 USH - - - - Idling
12:42:00.53 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:00.54 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:00.57 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:01.33 USH - - - - Idling
12:42:01.75 LSH - - - - Idling
12:42:01.77 SWS - - - - Idling
12:42:04.39 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:04.40 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:04.41 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:42:04.90 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
12:42:05.18 SWS - - - - Idling
12:42:05.61 LSH - - - - Idling
12:42:05.61 USH - - - - Idling
12:42:17.13 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:17.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:17.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:51.08 --- - - - - *** profile 10 down to 100 ft?
12:42:57.35 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
12:45:24.48 --- - - - - *** run at 100 ft
12:47:02.80 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:47:04.55 SWS 173.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:47:15.10 --- - - - - *** 11 deg
12:47:29.22 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:47:30.97 SWS -5.9 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:49:31.33 --- - - - - *** 12 deg

```

12:56:21.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:03:06.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:03:50.45	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:03:52.24	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:04:33.53	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:04:35.32	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:05:16.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:05:22.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile ascent
13:05:29.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 11
13:15:28.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:17:21.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:21.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:21.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:30.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:30.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:30.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:31.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:17:31.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:31.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:31.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:34.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:34.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:35.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:17:35.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:35.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:35.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:36.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:36.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:36.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:37.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:37.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:37.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:38.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:38.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:38.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:17:39.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:39.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:39.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:17:53.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:53.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:53.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:50.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** high level run
13:26:17.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
13:26:42.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 12
13:26:57.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:37:53.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 14 descent
13:38:06.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:06.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:06.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:07.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:38:07.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:07.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:08.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:24.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:48:35.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** im cloud run
13:48:53.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 11 3500 ft
13:49:02.62	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:49:04.45	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:51:10.15	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:51:11.95	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.

13:51:23.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:23.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:23.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:24.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:51:24.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:24.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:24.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:27.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:27.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:27.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:27.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:51:28.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:28.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:28.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:57:24.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:57:57.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:57:58.96	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:58:57.60	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:58:59.39	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:59:36.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:36.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:36.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:37.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:59:37.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:38.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:21.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:21.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:21.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:34.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:34.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:34.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:35.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:00:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:35.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:35.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:36.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:36.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:36.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:36.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:37.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:37.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:38.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:38.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:38.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:38.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:39.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:39.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:40.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:40.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:41.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:41.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:55.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:55.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:55.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:19.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:02:24.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:02:24.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:25.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:27.77	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 30ms.
14:02:29.96	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:02:34.59	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
14:02:36.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:36.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:37.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:38.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:38.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:46.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:46.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:49.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:49.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:49.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:55.49	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 15ms.
14:02:56.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:57.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:02:57.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:02:58.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:02:59.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:09.56	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 20ms.
14:03:11.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:12.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:13.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:14.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:16.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:03:18.65	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:03:33.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:34.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:51.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:53.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:03:54.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:03:55.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:34.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:35.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:39.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:40.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:55.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:56.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:57.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:57.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:05:58.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:04.77	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 50ms.
14:06:07.83	LSH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
14:06:10.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:11.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:06:13.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:14.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:17.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:23.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:06:23.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:06:25.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:07:06.29	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:07:08.09	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:08:20.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:08:46.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:47.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:08:49.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:53.05	LSH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
14:08:55.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:55.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:08:56.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:08:59.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:59.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:00.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:02.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:03.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:03.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:08.00	LSH	-	-	5	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 5ms.
14:09:10.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:10.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:11.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:12.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:13.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:09:59.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:11:48.76	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:11:50.55	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:12:41.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:14:05.91	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:14:07.69	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:28.48	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:16:30.25	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:18:45.79	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:18:47.55	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:18:54.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:19:21.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:21.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:21.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:31.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:31.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:31.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:32.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:19:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:32.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:32.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:33.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:33.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:33.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:34.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:34.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:35.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:36.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:36.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:36.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:37.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:19:37.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:37.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:38.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:38.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:38.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:39.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:39.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:39.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:40.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:40.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:40.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:19:41.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:41.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:41.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:19:52.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:52.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:19:52.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:29.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
14:23:05.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3500 ft in cloud
14:23:23.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:23:25.73	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:25:03.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** current run is run 13
14:25:13.63	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:25:15.43	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:27:04.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:27:05.87	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:27:18.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:18.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:19.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:27:19.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:27:19.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:20.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:20.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:30:14.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
14:31:11.20	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:31:12.99	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:33:00.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:35:44.97	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:35:46.81	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:37:05.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:05.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:05.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:05.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:37:06.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:06.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:09.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:37:10.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:10.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:10.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:29.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13\deg
14:38:37.44	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:38:39.23	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:38:42.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:42.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:42.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:42.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

14:38:42.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:43.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:43.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:46.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** end og run
14:44:51.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
14:45:50.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:47:30.60	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:47:32.40	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:51:32.13	---	-	-	-	-	***
14:51:42.32	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:51:44.15	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:52:02.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:02.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:02.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:10.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:10.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:10.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:11.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:52:11.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:11.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:11.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:14.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:14.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:14.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:14.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:52:15.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:15.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:16.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:16.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:16.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:17.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:17.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:17.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:18.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:18.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:18.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:19.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:19.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:19.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:20.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:20.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:20.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:20.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:21.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:21.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:22.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:22.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:22.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:22.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:23.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:23.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:36.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:36.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:36.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:04.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
14:53:48.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:48.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:48.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:53:49.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:53:49.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

14:53:49.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:53:49.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:57:43.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
14:59:23.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through cloud
14:59:59.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** now cloud top 3300 ft
15:04:36.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
15:04:53.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of decent start of climb
15:06:24.34	---	-	-	-	-	***
15:06:50.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
15:09:21.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:21.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:22.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:22.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:34.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:34.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:34.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:35.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:09:35.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:35.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:35.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:37.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:37.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:37.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:38.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:38.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:39.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:40.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:40.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:40.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:41.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:09:41.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:41.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:41.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:43.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:43.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:43.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:09:44.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:45.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:45.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:09:52.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:52.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:09:53.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:13:17.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:15:08.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:08.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:08.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:16.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:16.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:16.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:17.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:15:17.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:17.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:18.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:19.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:19.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:19.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:20.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:20.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:20.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:21.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:21.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:15:21.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:22.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:22.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:22.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:23.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:23.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:23.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:24.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:24.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:25.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:37.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:37.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:54.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile from 100 ft to 2000 ft
15:16:58.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2000 ft
15:20:19.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:22:11.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:26:21.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:26:23.14	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:27:46.86	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:27:48.66	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:28:02.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:28:10.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb to 5000 ft
15:30:43.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:43.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:43.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:57.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:57.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:57.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:58.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:30:58.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:58.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:58.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:30:59.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:59.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:59.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:00.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:00.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:01.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:01.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:01.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:01.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:02.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:03.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:03.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:05.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:05.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:05.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:31:06.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:06.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:06.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:31:17.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:17.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:17.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:24.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 5000 ft
15:31:39.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:32:07.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 17
15:33:51.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:51.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:51.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:33:52.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:33:52.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:53.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:53.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:57.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:58.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:06.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:35:17.71	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:35:19.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:35:35.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** scattered cloud below
15:36:26.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:36:29.19	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:36:31.04	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:36:33.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:33.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:33.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:41.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:41.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:41.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:41.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:36:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:42.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:42.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:44.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:44.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:44.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:44.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:36:44.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:45.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:45.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:46.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:46.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:46.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:47.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:47.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:47.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:48.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:48.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:48.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:49.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:49.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:50.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:36:58.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:58.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:58.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:12.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:47:39.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:49:10.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:49:27.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:51:40.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:55:10.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:11.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:11.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:20.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:55:21.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:21.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:21.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:55:22.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:22.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:22.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:23.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:23.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:23.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:24.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:24.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:24.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:25.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:25.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:25.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:26.33	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
15:55:29.29	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 15ms.
15:55:29.30	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 15ms.
15:55:31.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:31.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:31.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:55:32.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:32.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:32.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:33.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:33.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:33.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:33.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:34.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:34.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:34.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:34.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:34.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:35.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:35.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:35.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:36.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:36.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:36.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:37.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:37.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:38.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:38.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:39.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:39.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:39.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:39.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:40.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:46.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:46.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:46.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:38.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:56:40.02	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:56:46.42	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:56:48.22	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:56:55.79	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
15:57:12.69	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -60.000
15:57:16.54	SWS	-60.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:57:21.19	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
15:57:22.71	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000
15:57:23.67	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.500
15:57:25.25	SWS	-7.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -7.000

15:57:26.22	SWS	-7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.500
15:57:27.14	SWS	-6.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:57:28.18	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -5.500
15:57:30.96	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:57:38.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:57:38.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:57:38.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

Flight:

B411

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B411

Date: 30/oct/08

Instruments

CVI -	ok
Neph –PSAP – wetNeph	ok
SWS -	ok, using manual shutter control
SHIMS -	upper ok but evidence of not being cleaned before flight Lower recovered later in flight
AMS	some data from return leg, instrument requires work
Core Chem -	CO good, using manual calcs SO2 ok Nox ok O3 ozone overheat due to high cabin temperatures before flight
Cloud physics -	evidence of instrument noise generated by other kit on aircraft FSSP – some hard disc crashes – annoyance rather than important
ARIES -	ok
MARSS -	ok, possible no data until run 3.1
CCN -	ok except for blue screen of death for 13:17 -> 13:27
VACC -	good operation PAN ok CPC – tests required
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

Printer not responding although connected to network – needs sorting

Mission Scientist 1 Ethernet connection at cabin wall broken by brute strength of MS1. temp fix by connection to old point by spare cable.

Spare laptop required for MS3 position

ISDN Emails

1 email

MPDS

Run for approx 4 hours

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Issues

Aircraft cabin hot preflight

Upper BBRs need cleaning before every flight

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 30/10/8

Flight No: B 411

Pre-Flighter: Grafton

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☐	CNC	Butanol filled	} left to operators
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☐	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	} ** Check no butanol** } RT/cone } chem to complete
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>Signed</u>
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

B411 CPC Plots

B411 CPC Plot 1

B411 CPC Plot 3

B411 CPC Plot 2

B411 CPC Plot 4

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B411:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
MARSS	No log, set running by Jeff then monitored in flight by Stuart Rogers
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	17 Feb 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_101332_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_111332_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_121332_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_131332_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_101321_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_111321_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_121321_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_131321_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_141321_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_151321_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_101324_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_111324_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_121324_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_131324_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_141324_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_151324_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_101327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_111327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_121327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_131327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_141327_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081030_r0_b411_151327_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.